

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF IDEALS AND NORMS OF HISTORICAL KNOWLEDGE AT HERODOTUS'S HISTORY

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Abstract

The article examines the main approaches to the formation of Herodotus' initial ideals and norms of historical scientific knowledge. The main attention is paid to the ideals and norms of description and explanation, as well as the ideals and norms of evidence and validity of historical knowledge. The ideological and methodological foundations on which Herodotus builds his own system of ideals and norms of science are revealed.

Keywords: historical science, Ancient Greece, Herodotus, worldview foundations, methodology of historical cognition, ideals and norms of historical knowledge, ideals and norms of description and explanation, ideals and norms of evidence and validity.

The most important element of the foundations of science are the ideals and norms of science. They include the ideals and norms of: 1) evidence and justification of knowledge, 2) explanation and description; 3) construction and organization of knowledge. In their content, one can find several interconnected levels. The first of them is the normative structures common to any scientific research, distinguishing science from other forms of knowledge (everyday knowledge, religious and mythological reflection of the world, etc.). At each stage, this level is concretized by means of historically transient attitudes characteristic of the science of the corresponding era; it expresses the style of thinking of this era and forms the second level in the content of the ideals and norms of research. Finally, in the content of the ideals and norms of scientific research, one can distinguish the third level. In it, the attitudes of the second level are concretized in relation to the specifics of the subject area studied by a particular science [8].

Before proceeding to the consideration of the implementation of the above-mentioned ideals and norms in Herodotus, it is necessary to make several comments. Firstly, the above-mentioned ideals and norms of scientific research are fully present in a sufficiently developed system of scientific knowledge. Herodotus is at the origins of historical science. Therefore, it is not possible to isolate and describe fully developed ideals and norms; they are still only being formed.

Secondly, this version of the structure of ideals and norms of science, namely this sequence of these elements, relates to a greater extent to natural science. With regard to historical science, it is obvious that one should begin with the ideals and norms of description and explanation.

Ideals and norms of description and explanation.

In the ideals and norms of description and explanation, first of all, the philosophical and ontological foundations of science, as well as the general ideas that form the picture of the world, find their concretization. In an integrated form, they find their reflection in the object and subject of cognitive activity.

The object that Herodotus set the goal of describing in the "History" is extremely broad. This is a single process of the historical development of mankind: the life of the peoples inhabiting all known lands, beginning in time with the first information about them, from prehistory, to the events witnessed by the author himself. The subject of the description is also quite broad: these are events that took place within the above-mentioned geographical boundaries and historical framework, as well as various information about the life of the peoples (history, customs, everyday life) inhabiting them [5, p. 145]. (However, as noted earlier, issues of socio-economic history and the history of culture were not described in the "History".) Such norms, first set by Herodotus, signified a qualitative leap in the course of the emergence of history as a science; they also became the first ideals of description and explanation in the context of constructing the concept of the historical process.

Ideals and Norms of Description in Herodotus's "History".

The logical consequence of a certain interpretation of the object and subject of historical research should be the answers to the questions: on what basis is this description made, what source material and why exactly will it be used by the scientist. And here Herodotus also acts as a discoverer, turning simultaneously to all (or most) of the sources available to him: documentary evidence, eyewitness accounts of events, stories of those who talked with eyewitnesses and participants in events, mythological narratives.

Documentary evidence as a basis for describing the historical process. For the ancient Greek historian of Herodotus's time, there was a huge problem in using them. Or rather, the problem was that there were simply no reliable written sources describing historical events. Unlike historiography in the East, in Hellas there was no tradition of writing chronicles; there were no chroniclers among Herodotus' predecessors [10, p. 23]. That is, before the "History" very little had been done in the

field of historiography: chronicles as a form of recording the historical process were only beginning to appear. Large city chronicles (Miletus, Sparta, Athens) were first compiled during the lifetime of Herodotus, and partly after his death [5, p. 142]. Herodotus, obviously, could not solve this problem in principle, but he did a colossal job of finding and using all available written evidence. From the point of view of modern science, their share in the total number of sources used by the author of the "History" is probably small: there are five times fewer of them than references to eyewitness accounts [10, p. 195]. But in the end, the documentary basis for the description of many episodes of the Greco-Persian Wars is very solid: a list of contingents of individual peoples in the army and navy of Xerxes; a list of expenses incurred by Sparta, its allied states, individual citizens; the boundaries of the policies; descriptions of court procedures, etc. – could not have been obtained from oral sources, but exclusively from documents [2, p. 16-22].

Eyewitness accounts as the basis for historical writing. This component is the main one (in terms of volume and content) in Herodotus's work. This is due to two factors. Firstly, objective: the lack of a proper historiographical tradition, the insufficiency of written sources, as mentioned earlier. Secondly, subjective, Herodotus's own methodological approach: "... it is my duty to convey everything that is told, but, of course, I am not obliged to believe everything. And I will follow this rule in all my historical work" [10, p. 331]. The author of the "History" sought to preserve any information about "what was".

Indeed, he did not have the opportunity to refer "to predecessors". Of course, they wrote about the Greco-Persian wars before him, but no one did it with such detail and fundamentality. Herodotus himself was not a direct eyewitness of the events he described. As a result, he had to act as a true "historian", traveling around cities and countries and obtaining "testimonies" from eyewitnesses of those events [10, p. 330]. When collecting information about more ancient events, Herodotus relied on the rich oral tradition, writing down everything that local residents told him and preserving this information for history. In addition, he carefully collected written evidence of the events described in the "History", conveying them in great detail and indicating their witnesses as his predecessors. Thus, the detailed descriptions he provides of the meetings on the development of Miletus' strategy in relation to its opponents leave no doubt that he relied on the testimony of their eyewitness. This was none other than Hecataeus [10, p. 195], from whose works Herodotus drew this information. Thus, Herodotus's fundamental attitude to these sources of description of historical events consisted in preserving the messages he received if they seemed to him "worthy of attention" [5, p. 151]. As a result, information was preserved for history that Herodotus himself considered unreliable, but from a modern point of view they contain valuable and reliable material [ibid.]. (The interpretation of the term "worthy of attention" will be considered later; it substantively relates to the "ideals and norms of evidence and substantiation of knowledge").

Mythology as a meaningful source for constructing a model of the historical process. As noted earlier, Herodotus's worldview obviously contains elements of a mythological attitude to the surrounding world. And they are necessarily evident in the text of the "History" [10, p. 210]. However, unlike his logographer predecessors, they are of secondary importance in Hecataeus: mythological prehistory is present, but the main attention is paid to describing the history and life of the peoples contemporary to him [5, p. 145]. Herodotus adheres to the same principles of rational understanding of myths as Hecataeus, but they are included in his work as a kind of tribute to tradition and are completely atypical for the main text [ibid., p. 104]. In essence, the "History" contains only elements of rationalistic criticism of myths [7, p. 48], while in his predecessors they occupy the main place in the narratives. In relation to stories presented in mythological form, the general principle of recording information related to the description of the historical process is especially clear and consistent. As noted earlier, in the preface to the "History" the author sees his main task in collecting, preserving and passing on to descendants both what was known before him and information collected by him personally. Not criticism, but preservation [5, p. 147] is an important and entirely worthy task for a historian. As a result of its implementation, Herodotus preserves for history a number of reports that he personally considered unreliable, but in fact contained, as is now clear, valuable and reliable material. Sometimes what Herodotus himself did not believe (for example, that the Kerch Strait freezes in winter), but nevertheless wrote about it in his work, is now recognized as an absolutely unconditional fact [10, p. 330]. Thus, it is necessary to emphasize once again that the key principle of the "father of history" - openness to any information - turned out to be very fruitful in relation not only to mythological plots, but also to information from contemporary history.

The above does not mean that Herodotus simply records the myths known to him. In fact, he carries out a rational "reworking" of mythology, and a fundamentally deeper one than, for example, Hecataeus. The latter paid primary attention to understanding myths with the aim of finding in them the genealogical roots of contemporaries. Herodotus understands myths as a whole, eliminating their "spirit", but preserving the "letter" [ibid., p. 210]. Everything that was truly miraculous in the myths, incomprehensible with the help of reason, is eliminated, and it is given a natural explanation, plausible from the point of view of Herodotus. (Thus, contrary to the myth of the formation of the Tempe Valley by Poseidon, Herodotus clearly states that it appeared as a result of an earthquake [7, p. 48]). In this way, the author of the "History" breaks with the tradition of attitude to mythology, characteristic of logographers, when supernatural phenomena of the past were smoothly and directly connected with the present. He begins to form his own norms of its interpretation - mythology was subject to explanation by natural causes. And on the basis of a rational understanding of prehistory, the following element of ideals and norms of description and explanation arises.

Ideals and Norms of Explanation in Herodotus's History.

When considering the ideals and norms of explanation on which Herodotus's work is based, it is necessary to first pay attention to several essential aspects.

First, it should be noted that the development of ideals and norms of explanation within the framework of historical science is a much more complex and lengthy process than the formation of description norms. When forming the latter, the first historians could focus on the already existing tradition of historical writing formed by the chroniclers of the East. One could disagree with it, one could criticize it, but some basis already existed. But the tradition of explaining historical events did not exist, if we do not take into account mythology. The task of chroniclers was to describe events; their mission was accomplished. But in Ancient Greece, as already noted, a fundamentally new, unique, previously unheard of type of description appeared - "historical" - focused not on a simple presentation of events, but on "investigation and research", on the search for the causes of what was happening. Description for the historian was only a starting point from which he had to move on. In this regard, Herodotus was obviously the first to develop ideals and norms for explaining events. And the more difficult was the task of finding the causes of the historical process, which he set for himself explicitly.

Secondly, the search for "natural causes" of the events described in myths actually included two interconnected, but not identical tasks: identifying the "causes" and interpreting events on a "natural" basis. This epistemological complexity also determined a certain inconsistency in Herodotus's solution.

It should be noted that the recognition of the presence of certain suprapersonal causes was also present in the mythological worldview. But Herodotus in the preface to "History" outlines a fundamentally different goal - the study of the causes of real historical events [1, p. 469]. What happened in history, in his opinion, is not accidental: the present is conditioned by the past, the future - by the present, but everything that happens has causes. And they should be found and understood in order to use this knowledge in the future. The initial premises of the search for these causes are embedded in the very picture of the world of Herodotus: on the basis of the unity of historical space and time, there is a universal history. And it must necessarily contain *a universal cause of what is happening*, complementing and strengthening the understanding of history as a holistic process.

While Herodotus establishes this fundamentally important methodological position, he is still unable to reveal its content based on natural factors. Therefore, the "father of history" thinks contradictorily about the content of this universal cause, departs from strict and consistent "naturalness" and, in essence, does not go beyond the framework of the mythological worldview. From Herodotus's point of view, the universal cause of events that make up the historical process is indisputable fate, or destiny. Blind fate punishes anyone who seizes (or wants to seize) more happiness than is destined for him - this is the fundamental law of history,

realized in a single historical process and explaining everything that happens. The entire "History" is constructed, in essence, as a collection of specific illustrations of this general position [5, p. 41]. The defeat of the Persians in the Greco-Persian Wars, according to Herodotus, is entirely natural, it is also only a special case of the manifestation of a general cosmic law [3, p. 13]. The recognition of the general law introduced certain adjustments to the implementation of the original principle stated in the preface: the preservation of everything that is known. This general idea served as a methodological basis for the selection of versions of stories recorded in the "History" and narrating certain events. In some cases, this led to historical distortion - of the possible versions of the description of events known to him, Herodotus accepted the worst version instead of the best [ibid., p. 42]. Thus, Herodotus's understanding of the universal fundamental cause that determines the course of a single historical process is internally contradictory. On the one hand, in the substantive interpretation of this cause, he does not go beyond the mythological worldview. At the same time, the very recognition of the existence of a fundamental cause for all history in methodological terms meant a serious step in the formation of a unified scientific historiography. It should be noted that this idea subsequently, beginning immediately with Thucydides, disappears from historical science for millennia, appearing in it only in the New Age [5, p. 158].

But the will of the deity, the subordination of man to fate - all this for Herodotus is only *one side of the world order*. The "Father of History" does not limit himself to recognizing only the universal superhuman historical causality, which was one of the components of the mythological picture of the world. He identifies another factor influencing the historical process. The course of history is also determined by the actions of specific people and personified states in the person of their rulers. Therefore, *the actions of people, determined by their characters, motives and goals - the second component of historical causality* [5, p. 157]. In its implementation, another universal law is manifested - the law of retribution for human actions. All people inevitably pay for their deeds. As a result, human life, as Herodotus shows, is not only predetermined from above, but also depends on the behavior of the people themselves. In this regard, the "History" laid the foundation for the methodological tradition of explaining the immediate course of history, characteristic of ancient historiography as a whole.

The direct driving force of the historical process in Herodotus is man: relations between people, their passions, vices [1, p. 489]. It is precisely from human relations, determined by the characters, virtues or vices of the participants, that it depends: whether this or that event will happen or not. In this case, the "father of history" emphasizes such qualities as courage and cowardice, envy and generosity, selflessness and greed. As a result, the causes of global historical events turn out to be petty, "everyday": the Greeks stole a woman from the Persians, the Persians, in turn, did the same, etc. [5, p. 158].

This approach to explaining specific historical events is quite natural. On the one hand, it follows from the remnants of ideas characteristic of the mythological worldview. Anthropomorphism - one of its most important substantive characteristics - meant likening the world to a specific person. However, the mythological worldview was gradually eliminated, and this approach in historiography remained. Consequently, to the greatest extent, such a methodological approach was conditioned by the basic principles of ancient philosophy throughout its existence. The harmony of the Cosmos as a whole meant the harmony of its individual parts. Man as a microcosm was understood as complete and self-sufficient; all the reasons for his actions were contained in him. This idea was dominant in all ancient philosophy. (Thus, Aristotle, giving a classification of causality, singled out the target as one of the most important. In his interpretation, the primary cause of human activity is his goal, and it is determined by character.) In this case, we can clearly state the direct influence of the philosophical foundations of culture on the formation of the methodological principles of history as a science. Ancient historians made a "*tacit and unconscious assumption* (emphasis mine – S.M.) that the causes that could be taken into account in a historical work were only the immediate causes and experiences of individuals or personified states" [5, p. 158]. As a result, the outcome of the historical process arose on the basis of the unity of the actions of suprapersonal world forces (general law) and the actions of people pursuing their own interests in specific historical events. Herodotus thus made a significant step forward in interpreting the natural causes of historical events. With regard to explaining the outcome of the Greco-Persian Wars, this second angle of view on events allowed Herodotus to interpret the victory of the Greeks not only as a phenomenon of cosmic scale, but also as an ethical fact, not only as the fulfillment of the will of the gods, but also as a manifestation of the moral superiority of the Hellenes over the Persians [3, p. 13]. The Hellenes won because they were brave, and they were brave because they were free and subject only to the law, not to the wishes of their rulers.

In general, this approach to explaining history allowed Herodotus to create the first holistic model of the historical process. By capturing the repetition of the same pattern over a three-hundred-year change of generations, the "father of history" was able to depict the Greco-Persian wars not as separate events, significant only for their participants, but inextricably linked with the course of world history [3, p. 12], as a necessary element of the holistic historical process.

Ideals and norms of evidence and validity.

Ideals and norms of evidence and validity determine the concrete historical content of the concept of "true knowledge" and the methods of obtaining it. For historical science, these ideals and norms of scientific research are undoubtedly of primary importance. Here, as in the natural sciences, it is impossible to obtain some unambiguously recorded information about objects and processes (based on description, measurement) directly during their existence, which in themselves will gradually form the empirical level of

knowledge. But information about historical events is obtained post factum and cannot be verified directly. At the same time, in order to be used in the course of historical writing, they must immediately be understood by the scientist for truth or falsity. That is, the historian must have verification methods and use them simultaneously with obtaining information related to the subject being studied. In other words, the process of developing standards of validity and evidence during the period of the emergence of history as a science occurred simultaneously with the accumulation of relevant knowledge, as a result of which it was objectively more complex than in relation to other ideals and norms of scientific research. And Herodotus was the first of the authors known to us, the analysis of whose work allows us to identify certain ideals and norms of validity and evidence (in relation to the period of the formation of history as a science, it is obviously appropriate to use exactly this sequence of these terms). Assessing Herodotus from the point of view of reliability and evidence, most researchers admit that "the main shortcoming of his book is that, in contrast to Thucydides, he was unable to see the fundamental difference between the fabulous material relating to time immemorial and the historical facts of recent times" [5, pp. 149 - 150]. This assessment is certainly correct, but at the same time it is too general in nature and therefore requires specification in relation to the various types of information recorded in the "History". But first, it is necessary to pay attention to several substantive aspects.

First, as noted earlier, Herodotus' worldview contains elements of a mythological worldview. This does not simply mean that he knew mythology better than his followers. The world itself had mythological features for him, so the line between events that were natural and fabulous was not as clear as it seemed to Thucydides.

Second, Herodotus was the first who really began to evaluate the information he received in any comprehensive way. At the same time, his methods seem to "fall out" of the logic of the development of the historical science of antiquity. Hecataeus (before Herodotus), as noted earlier, stated that he wrote as he "seemed true". The attitude is indeed correct, but at the same time very subjective - what is true for one is not so for another. Thucydides (after the "father of history") strengthens the element of "truth": he records events that he witnessed, or that he heard from others, but after precise research regarding each fact [10, p. 210]. Herodotus, as it were, takes a step back, "conveys everything that is said," while specifying that "he is not obliged to believe everything" [ibid., p. 211]. And this clarification, as will be shown later, fundamentally changes the actual content of the methodological position recorded in the first part of his statement.

Thirdly, the goal stated in the preface to the "History" is not comparable with either predecessors (this is obvious) or followers. Herodotus describes historical events much more extensively and comprehensively, forms an image of a single historical process. And to describe it, it is necessary, if possible, to "know everything". This attitude necessarily requires some "lowering" of the level of reliability of the material used.

Fourthly, the fact that one of the epistemological prerequisites of philosophy as the first form of scientific knowledge is a mythological worldview means the presence of certain transitional forms of fixation of scientific knowledge. And in the work of the "father of history" this is manifested quite clearly. The very process of formation of historical thought in Ancient Greece in this regard is a movement from vague images to accessible and understandable images and further to semi-images [11, p. 23], to concepts-images. And the latter are very widely presented in the "History". And for this form of knowledge, the definition of truth is, in principle, quite complex. Thus, in the "History" the ideals and norms of validity and evidence are only beginning to form.

Therefore, there is a certain contradiction and inconsistency here. Nevertheless, it was on the basis of this understanding that the first historical work was created. Therefore, we will try to analyze those substantive aspects and approaches that formed the basis for the further development of the methodological base of historical research.

First, it is necessary to determine a possible list of questions that (one way or another, explicitly or implicitly) a historian had to answer when writing his work, that is, *when transforming the initial information* that he possessed into natural (from his point of view) elements of scientific narration (that is, knowledge that should be recorded in a historical description) - *into scientific and historical facts*. This list is obviously far from complete, but it allows us to clarify and concretize the substantive elements of the process of forming the methodology of scientific research among the founders of historical science. So:

1. information about what aspects of society interests the author;
2. what are the sources of obtaining this information. The scientist could use all the data available to him or determine a specific list of them;
3. whether the obtained data is subject to verification for truth or not, if such verification is possible in principle;
4. how exactly it is carried out; what is the nature of the tools used: subjective (criticality, rational understanding, etc.), objective (comparison with reliable written evidence, with artifacts);
5. on what grounds is the decision made to include the resulting material in the text;
6. whether comments are given on the status of the materials included in the work (true, probable, implausible, questionable, false, etc.). And if this information is assessed as true after processing, then it is given *the status of a fact* - the formation of *the empirical basis of historical science* begins.

It should be immediately emphasized that Herodotus was not limited to only direct and immediate "work" with the information received, which was also typical of his followers. In addition, when creating "History," logical manipulation of facts was carried out in accordance with two procedures: movement from the particular (specific information) to the general and from the general to the particular, which is a feature of the method of the "father of history."

So, let us consider the procedures for converting the information collected by Herodotus into substantive elements, eventually included in his work.

It should be noted that ancient historians paid primary and fundamental attention to political events, and most of them can be called "purely political" [10, p. 353]. Herodotus, in comparison, is a much more encyclopedic author in terms of his coverage of reality. He collects information about the most diverse aspects of the life of the Hellenes and barbarians (although, as noted earlier, he does not have socio-economic history or cultural history) [ibid., p. 354].

For this, he uses, as already noted, all sources available to him. Some of them had the status of truth from the very beginning (specific documents, memoirs of direct participants in events with very precise details) and did not require additional assessment from this point of view: they fit into the historical context. It was necessary to comprehend the collected memories and stories of people for their correspondence to real historical events, and also to somehow characterize the accumulated mythological legends, fairy tales, etc. It is worth dwelling on Herodotus's "processing" of this component of the original information, since it is here that the options for the "validity" of their inclusion in the text of the "History" are most clearly manifested.

Let us recall the fundamental position of the "father of history" - he is obliged to preserve everything that he is told, even if he himself does not believe it. "It is my duty to convey everything that is told, but, of course, I am not obliged to believe everything" [10, p. 211]. It would seem that the approach is quite clear and simple. As a result of its implementation, a huge amount of materials should have accumulated that are of no value at all from the point of view of science. But in reality, the focus not on harsh criticism of existing information, but on its careful collection and preservation, leads to a significantly different result. Herodotus preserves for history a whole series of reports that he personally considers unreliable, but from the point of view of subsequent science contain valuable and reliable material [5, p. 145]. In other words, he does not simply collect everything he hears, but rather interprets and classifies it in a certain way from the point of view of reliability.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the fact that the History does not always present different versions of events. This happens only when the author is not completely sure that one of them is correct. But even in this case, Herodotus is almost never satisfied with simply reporting different versions, but, as a rule, indicates which version and for what reasons seems reliable to him [ibid., p. 146]. He had a lot of material at his disposal and in all cases when he had a plausible story at his disposal, he rejected all other versions. Only in cases when the "father of history" had no arguments to give preference to one version or another, he presents both, without subjecting them to critical evaluation [ibid., p. 147]; each of them had, from his point of view, a certain reliability. And besides them, there were others. Obviously, Herodotus, in fact, did not consider himself obliged to always report all the versions known to him [ibid., p. 149]. That is, when writing the History,

he deviated from the stated principle of "reporting everything." Consequently, he used certain internal criteria to assess the credibility of the information included in the book. The mere fact of the existence of such criteria did not necessarily mean that they were correct and impeccable, but overall they ensured the selection of the appropriate primary material. Researchers of Herodotus's work clearly acknowledge that "in the purely historical and ethnographic parts... Herodotus, in his assessments of sources, was guided by a *generally good historical intuition* (emphasis mine – S.M.)" [ibid., p. 150]. And much of the information provided in the History was later confirmed, although both in Herodotus's time and later, they were considered fiction [ibid., p. 157]. Thus, the original statement about the desire to "preserve everything" with the addition of the clarification "I am not obliged to believe everything" turned into its opposite: Herodotus includes in his "History" and, thus, gives the status of a scientific fact to evidence that he repeatedly critically comprehends, compares with others, that is, verifies them (in modern terminology). In other words, in reality, when selecting information for inclusion in the text of his work, he tries to give them a multifaceted objective assessment.

This *focus on objectivity* was an absolutely necessary element in substantiating the correctness of his "History" as a version of the presentation of the historical process. However, the focus itself did not mean the presence of some absolute objectivity and consisted of several substantive aspects. Let us consider them according to the degree of methodological significance.

First, *the political aspect*. Herodotus was a representative of the slave-owning class as a whole and a supporter of a specific socio-political grouping within this class, namely, the Athenian democracy headed by Pericles [5, p. 151]. This must be taken into account when evaluating his messages. Athenian democracy was a historically progressive movement during the life of the "father of history". It replaced the old aristocracy, preserved from the royal period of ancient history, and ensured the active development of handicraft production, trade, art, philosophy, etc. But Herodotus's focus on Athenian democracy was not unconditional: characterizing specific forms of states, he did not unequivocally assert that any democracy is good and any monarchical power is evil, but tried to give specific assessments of real state institutions.

Secondly, *the general historical aspect*. Herodotus was the first universal historian [ibid., p. 151]. He did not limit himself to the framework of one state or one people. He tries to understand the logic of all participants in the Greco-Persian wars: both the Greeks - representatives of various city-states (Athens, Sparta, Miletus, etc.), and their enemies. As noted earlier, the very origin of the "father of history" contributed to this - being a Hellene, he was born and raised in Halicarnassus as a Persian subject; as a result, he belonged to both cultural "worlds" [10, p. 231]. For him, the wars described were not a simple series of battles. He tried to give the broadest and most complete picture of them. And the logical continuation of this aspiration is the following substantive aspect of Herodotus' objectivity.

Thirdly, *the systemic aspect*. Herodotus sought to give a comprehensive and holistic description of events, constantly searching for their hidden foundations: what causes caused the war, why the course of military operations turned out to be exactly this way, etc. In the "History" one event gives rise to another, their cause-and-effect chains are formed. The "Father of History", therefore, already actively poses not only the questions "when?", "who?" and "how?", but also "why did they happen?" [ibid., p. 230]. It should be noted that the latter question, according to a number of philosophers of the New Age, primarily positivists, does not relate to the subject of historical science: it should be dealt with by the philosophy of history. The historian should only collect facts. But Herodotus did not follow this path, choosing other methodological guidelines [ibid., p. 231]. He sought to illuminate the Greco-Persian wars systematically: not as a set, a simple set of events, but as a connected sequence, united by internal logic. The solution to this problem was impossible on the basis of a simple listing of facts - a certain amount of work with them was required.

And Herodotus does it. As already noted, unlike logographers, who limited themselves to general philosophical premises in examining the world and society, he is, first of all, an empiricist [5, p. 151]; he constantly monitors real historical events, but does not limit himself to simple observation. And where possible, he generalizes observations. Of course, this led to a certain narrowness of outlook, but at the same time provided a more objective and therefore more valuable approach to the facts for historical research of our time, laid the *foundation for their logical comprehension and the formation of a method of transition from the particular to the general in historical science*.

But the "father of history" does not limit himself to this. His work also contains *the following logical method – movement from the general to the particular*. The general patterns identified, which determine the unity of the historical process, begin to be used to assess the truth of the collected information. In some cases, Herodotus deliberately changes the chronology of events (and this was already noted by Thucydides), includes in the text of his work incorrect information, but corresponding to the general historical law in his understanding, as opposed to real, but not corresponding to it [5, pp. 42 - 43].

This position is well illustrated by the following example. Herodotus willingly accepted the popular legend that the solar eclipse was visible in western Asia in 480 BC, although in fact it was in 478 BC. He needed to move this miraculous phenomenon two years earlier so that it could be interpreted as a fatal sign before Xerxes set out on a campaign [ibid.].

This episode is quite indicative in terms of demonstrating the essential components of the methodology for constructing a picture of the historical process, which is used by the "father of history" in this case. Let us highlight the main elements of its implementation.

1. A pattern is constructed based on worldview attitudes (faith in gods, remnants of a mythological worldview) and some generalization of information: a

conclusion is made about the presence of general patterns in history. History is a single, integral process.

2. The general pattern of the historical process is revealed. As noted earlier, from Herodotus's point of view, the general cause of events that make up the historical process is *indisputable fate, or destiny*. Blind fate punishes anyone who seizes (or wants to seize) more happiness than is destined for him - this is *the main law of history*. The entire concept of "History" is built on this.

3. There is an understanding of two known options for dating events, the one that corresponds to the general concept is chosen. It is included in the text, acquiring the status of a historical fact. Since the scale of historical time in the "History" is epochal - decades and centuries - a deviation of two years is insignificant. Moreover, the eclipse - in accordance with the ideas of Herodotus - *should have taken place in the specified year*, since the gods were supposed to warn the ruler of the Persian Empire about the inadmissibility of such actions. Therefore, the real historical result of the beginning of the war of the Persians against the Greeks is quite natural, according to Herodotus: the union of the Greek city-states, whose capabilities are incomparably small in comparison with the Persians, wins. Chronological distortion, violation of historical sequence (that is, a negative example) has at the same time an important methodological significance: Herodotus, obviously, intuitively reveals the essential regularity of the functioning of science as a system of knowledge - the initial information is interpreted on the basis of previously formulated, already existing concepts.

In essence, there are the beginnings of theorizing in historical science: Herodotus seems to return to the legacy of the logographers, but on a qualitatively new level. Another substantive component of the validity of historical knowledge is formed - its assessment of truth or falsity is carried out on the basis of "fitting" into a certain concept of the historical process. Information

(primary empirical level) is assessed as true or false from the point of view of the formed concept (theoretical level). They must correspond to it! And the reflection of this pattern is found in the analysis of the following aspect of the ideals and norms of scientific research.

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